

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
RGN 21 & RM 16 END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- DECEMBER 2018
MIP 11 MICROBIOLOGY & INFECTION PREVENTION/CONTROL
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HRS.

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. State one function each of the following in the penetration of host defence mechanism.
- i. Fimbriae used by *Neisseria gonorrhoea* - 1 mark
 - ii. Mycolic acid of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. - 1 mark
- b. As a nurse/midwife, state Eight(8) practices that can lead to specimen rejection by a laboratory Technician. - 8 marks
- c. a State 5 mechanisms that the innate or natural immunity uses to avoid infections. - 10 marks

Question Two

- Hand washing is very important in our every day life especially a the ward
List the four (4) types of hand washing - 4 marks
- a. State six(6) barriers to frequent hand washing - 6 marks
 - b. Proper hand washing can break the chain in the disease transmission cycle. State the six(6) links in the disease transmission cycle. - 6marks
 - c. Enumerate four(4) host features that affects the risk of infection - 4 marks

Question Three

- a. Define the following terms
- i. Critical items - 1 mark
 - ii. Semi critical items - 1mark
 - iii. Non critical items - 1mark
- b. Classify the following in a tabular form under critical, semi-critical and non-critical items:
- a. Bone chisel,
 - b. Sims speculum,
 - c. crutches,
 - d. stethoscope,
 - e. plate(implant)
 - f. anesthesia breathing circuit,
 - g. scalpels,
 - h. sphygmomanometer,
 - i. cytoscope,
 - j. bed board,
 - k. cutting scissors,
 - l. Cuffed endotracheal tube. - 6 marks

- c. A health facility had their chlorine solution out of stock with only bleach powder in stock. Calculate the number of grams of bleach powder for each litre of water if they are to prepare 0.5% chlorine from the bleach powder which contains 40% active chlorine. - 6 marks
- d. State the guidelines for putting on gown. - 5mark

NMTC – BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS, DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – DECEMBER 2016
RGN 19 & RM 14 (MIP 111) MICROBIOLOGY & INFECTION PREVENTION / CONTROL
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HRS
ESSAY

Instructions:

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate booklet*
- *Each question carries 20marks*
- *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

Question One

- a. Mr. Jackson was rushed to your facility. He was later diagnosed of pneumococcal meningitis.
- i. State four symptoms of this disease. - 2 marks
 - ii. Mention two ways of transmitting this disease - 2 marks
 - iii. What is the causative organism? - 1 mark
 - iv. List four conditions suitable for the growth of bacteria. - 2 marks
 - v. State three importance of Gram staining technique - 3 marks
- b. i. State four (4) Ecological factors that affect micro-organism. - 2mks
- ii. How would you as a nurse/midwife guide patient at your ward to produce.
Midstream or clean- catch urine specimen for culture and sensitivity. - 6mks
- iii. State the toxin released by vibrio cholera and clostridium tetani organism. - 2mks

Question Two

As part of their 60 years anniversary celebration, you were invited by the Holy Family Hospital-Berekum, to address a group of newly recruited ward assistants on infection prevention and control.

- a. Outline the universal precautions associated with the handling and disposal of sharps (needles) in the ward. - 5 marks
- b. State the five (5) steps involved in instrument processing. - 5 marks
- c. Describe the procedure involved in the processing of used instruments after a wound dressing - 10 marks

Question Three

- a. Outline the basic principles of medical asepsis - 6 marks
- b. State any four (4) chemical sterilization method/agent
- c. Outline eight (8) Standard or Universal Precautions to a colleague first year student - 8 marks
- d. Outline Ten (10) indications for hand washing - 10 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
NMTC – BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION DECEMBER - 2015
RGN 18 MICROBIOLOGY & INFECTION PREVENTION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HRS
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Not that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a) What is disease transmission cycle? - 3 marks
- b) Mention three (3) route of entry of microorganism into the body. - 3 marks
- c) List eight (8) body fluids that may be infectious - 4 marks
- d) What is decontamination? - 3 marks
- e) Elaborate the process of decontamination of instrument [Scissors] - 7 marks

Question Two

- a) Briefly explain Antiseptic - 2 marks
- b. Mention steps that are involved in clinical hand washing - 8 marks
- c. During your first clinical you were asked by your ward in charge to prepare chlorine solution that has just been brought from the stores you observe that the concentration of the chlorine was 20%. Take the universal standard use. Show in calculation the amount of chlorine and water that will be needed to enable you get the right proportion to help you decontaminate your instrument - 4 marks
- d. What standard precautions will you follow when handling used needles in the ward - 6 marks

Question Three

- a) State five (5) importance of microbiology to the nurse or midwife - 5 marks
- b) a. Five children community X were diagnosed of amoebic dysentery in the lab of hospital Z
 - i) What is the causative organism? - 1 mark
 - ii) How is this organism transmitted - 2 marks
 - iii) State five ways of preventing and controlling the infection of this organism - 10 marks
- v) Explain the stages of Bacteria growth - 2 marks

Question Four

- a. State three (3) characteristics of the following groups of microorganisms
 - i. Bacteria
 - ii. Viruses
 - iii. Fungi- 9 marks
- b. State the causative agent of the following diseases
 - i. Tuberculosis
 - ii. Polio
 - iii. Cervical cancer
 - iv. Oral thrush
 - v. Tetanus
 - vi. Cholera- 6 marks
- c. Explain the role of the Nurse/Midwife in ensuring quality Laboratory result - 5 marks